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Creating a Smart Learning Space: Learning With and Learning From Student Generated Data about Learning

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ABSTRACT

In a course from our Social and Human Sciences master program, students are taught the social and behavioural sciences of learning (“learning sciences”). Students also learn how to conduct social and behavioural research by collecting data on campus during semester long projects. Proposed by internal “clients” from the school, the projects bring data on students learning both to teachers and to the institution, thus transforming the school into a lab for research and development on teaching and lifelong learning in science and engineering – a Smart Learning Space. This paper describes the design of this course together with examples of projects and their impact at different levels in the school. In particular, this course has laid the foundations for a culture of evidence-based and data-driven teaching and learning within the institution. We discuss the challenges we had to tackle as well as some perspectives for the future.

Conference Key Areas: Engineering Education Research, Continuing Engineering Education and Lifelong Learning

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INTRODUCTION

Engineers who graduate today will, in ten years' time, be working in a radically changed environment. Their ability to respond effectively will depend on their capacity to continue to learn and develop throughout their career. Hence, 'lifelong learning' has been identified as a key competence in engineering education [1, 2]. A second key issue in recent years has been the growing realization of the importance of evidence-informed teaching in science and engineering [3, 4] as well as more generally. An optional Learning Sciences course offered to Science and Engineering students has sought to address both these issues.

While the role of social and human sciences in engineering education is often ill defined, there is a clear rationale for including learning sciences and social and behavioural research skills within engineering programmes. Beyond the learning for students themselves, the data generated from learning research can inform educational decisions taken by learners, teachers and the school more generally, transforming the school itself into a teaching and research and development lab.

This paper will first outline the research base behind these concerns, will then describe the course and some of its outputs and will then look at its impact within the engineering school more generally.

1 RELATED WORK

Social and Human Sciences have been seen as a required component in the training of engineers for many decades [5]. Despite this fact, there remains a lack of clarity as to their role, with rationales offered including: (a) the development of personal qualities such as modesty, openness and creativity [6,7]; and (b) the development of 'professional skills' of working in multi-disciplinary teams, adopting ethical practice, being aware of social impacts and causes of technology, and communicating effectively in international and intercultural contexts [2].

Of any social scientific or humanities discipline, learning sciences has a particular and valuable role to play in engineering education. Lifelong learning has been identified as among the key 'professional' skills of engineers [1,2] and an ability to think about learning has been found to be associated both with increased attainment in formal education and with an increased ability to apply classroom learning to 'real-life' situations [8]. Learning sciences also plays a role in enhancing students' interdisciplinary competences since learning science is, by definition, an interdisciplinary space, drawing on neurology, sociology, educational psychology, information sciences, and anthropology. This mix of social, behavioural, and hard science disciplines provides a fertile space for engineering students to engage in the interface between disciplines. Studying how to research learning also provides practical skills in social research, while the ethical standards which apply in social and behavioural science research provide an opportunity to engage students in learning how to apply ethical principles such as self-determination, informed consent, vulnerable populations, as well as physical, psychological, and sociological risk.

Beyond these practical utilities for the learner, however, the study of learning sciences

also provides an opportunity for the engineering school as a whole to become a learning organization. There is now clear research evidence that many commonly used higher education teaching practices are found to be less effective than underused alternatives such as collaborative learning, concept maps, use of visualization technology, use of conceptually-oriented tasks, and use of interactive teaching approaches [3,4,9]. However, although this research evidence tells us that some methods of teaching and learning work better than others “in general” (that is, they are “evidence-informed”), their implementation in particular contexts and settings will often depend on locally-collected evidence about effectiveness – an approach which is known internationally as Scholarship of Teaching and Learning (SOTL) [10]. Engaging in learning sciences research can provide this evidence.

The next section describes one attempt to do this, in practice.

2 THE SMART LEARNING SPACE

Within the social and human sciences strand of courses, a learning sciences course has been offered at Master level in Ecole Polytechnique Fédérale de Lausanne (EPFL) since 2012. The course has two goals: (a) introducing students to learning sciences research, with a particular focus on what it has to say about how they themselves learn, and (b) teaching skills of designing and conducting a piece of quantitative research on learning.

Around 60 students register for the course each year with 45 to 55 continuing to complete the research project.

In the first semester, learning sciences are introduced through interactive lectures and through a series of in-class experiments. These experiments mean that students are confronted with data about their own learning in different situations which ensures that the findings are integrated by students at a personal level rather than being seen as abstract representation of learners “in general”. These classes also mean that students have an experience of how experiments and social surveys are actually designed. The experiments also generate real-life data which, in turn, is used in exercise/tutorial sessions by students to practice skills of social data analysis.

In the second semester, students use the knowledge and skills developed to carry out a research project, from the design phase to the reporting phase, in groups of 3 or 4. For the projects to be open-ended and realistic enough to provide an authentic and rich learning environment, project topics have to be research questions that can be answered with data collected locally. Students are assessed based upon a research report and a poster that they produce. In the first year of the course, students generated their own project titles, however from 2013 on, students were provided with a list of possible titles with each project being required to be (a) focused on learning and (b) of use to some stakeholder within the school (e.g., a teacher, other students, departments, or administrative units). Initially potential “clients” were largely sourced through personal connections by the teacher. Since 2014, the results of the student projects have been presented each year at a public poster session and again at the annual faculty retreat, and this has led to a growing interest in the projects within the school. In the academic year 2017-18 there are 13 different projects, with clients including teachers in Chemistry and Environmental Sciences, the school’s Marketing, Gender Equality, MOOC, and Teaching Support units, the Library, and the Vice Presidency for Innovation.

The research that students carry out within the school, in turn, feeds back into the

institution. It has helped teachers to test innovative teaching approaches and to validate their assessment methods. It has provided feedback on what Bachelor students have learned and where they struggle which, in turn, has allowed teachers to adjust their approaches to teaching and assessment. It has provided the school's pedagogic team with information about how students experience tutorials/exercises which in turn has allowed tutor training to be re-developed to better meet local needs. It has also provided data about learning which is fed back to students and which allows them reflect on and change their approaches to learning. In this sense, the course creates a virtuous cycle of individual learning, while producing data which allows for institutional learning. In this way, the whole school becomes a teaching and research and development lab in learning sciences. It is this idea that we refer to as the "Smart Learning Space".

Given that the research is being carried out by students who lack extensive training in learning sciences and in social research methods it is not surprising that the quality of their results can be variable. In many cases, however, the quality has been exceptional and a number of the studies have been presented by the students and the course teacher at international conferences.

3 RESULTS

Over the last five years, over 60 projects have been completed by students. While the projects have been diverse, a notable sub-set of projects has focused on the learning and challenges of our first-year students. Rather than present a random selection of different projects, a number of these projects which showed thematic continuity are presented in this section.

In 2014, one study compared exam grades from 236 first-year students with their score on an internationally normed test of conceptual understanding in classical mechanics called the Force Concept Inventory (FCI) [11]. The goal was to validate the course exam, and indeed the study showed that the exam did in fact test student conceptual understanding. However the data also showed that quite a few students who scored reasonably well when tested on their conceptual understanding still failed the exam. This data therefore made clear that, while understanding physics is a requirement for passing first-year courses in the institution, it is not enough [14].

One hypothesis to be explored as to the reasons for student failure was that the students were using inappropriate strategies in seeking to solve the problems. As Schoenfeld has noted, university exercises differ from those faced in high school in that high school exercises often require only the recognition of an exercise type and the application of an algorithm (called algorithmic exercises), while at university level exercises can often require the construction of an algorithm itself (referred to as problem-solving exercises) [12]. It was hypothesised that students were failing to recognise which exercises were simply algorithmic and which required actual problem solving. This idea was tested through a number of studies, looking at how students categorised mathematical problems [15], and through the use of a talk aloud protocol to explore the differences between student's self-reported problem solving approaches and their actual problem solving [16]. Further data was collected from a review of 136 first year student exams in order to catalogue the error types which arose most frequently [17].

The growing body of evidence within the school also prompted teachers to carry out their own studies. One, which focused on this question of student problem solving methods, also provided evidence that students who successfully identified an exercise as requiring a problem solving approach, and who understood how to apply such an approach, tended to be more successful in solving the kinds of complex problems posed in our first year exams [18].

Together, these studies provided convincing evidence that the difficulty for many of our students was not in their content knowledge, but in their methodological approach to problems and in their beliefs about such problems. This evidence has, in turn, led the school's Vice Presidency for Education in 2017 to adopt a strategic project on improving first year students' methodological skills in solving complex problems. This project draws on a number of strands including:

- A newly published book on problem solving and study skills for science and engineering students [19]
- A companion MOOC and learning companion website/app with in-built personal analytics to allow students to get direct feedback on aspects of their approaches to learning and problem solving
- An increased focus on modelling of and feedback on problem solving methods by professors
- A pilot project to assess the use of peer feedback as a tool in supporting students' learning of problem solving.

4 ISSUES AND CHALLENGES

While the impact and value of the course is evident, its development and implementation have not always been easy.

No resources have been allocated to the course since it started other than a single teacher who is responsible for managing teaching and experiments in a class of 60 learners and for overseeing between 13 and 18 projects each year. Resources required for gathering data, preparing posters, and for providing additional technical supervision and support for students have been begged or borrowed from supportive colleagues and units.

Secondly, ensuring that the projects were designed with an appropriate ethical basis was a challenge. Since the timeframe of the project was a single semester, students could not reasonably be asked to go through the time-consuming ethical approval process. At the same time, the projects needed to be ethical in their approach. The solution to this difficulty was to have a research protocol for the course pre-approved by the school's human research ethics committee which set a series of boundary conditions for the research projects. Students are required to demonstrate that their research design respects this protocol.

A third difficulty arises from the interdisciplinarity of the projects: students with training in mathematics, computational sciences, and machine learning are often able to apply sophisticated statistical and analytical techniques which are beyond the knowledge base of the teacher. This is an extremely desirable difficulty and demonstrates the exciting opportunities that arise in interdisciplinary fields. However it is also a challenge that needs to be carefully addressed in the assessment of the students' work. In such cases, clients have been invited to provide advice on the methods and techniques used, while the ultimate responsibility for grading rests with the teacher.

A more intractable difficulty arises from the dangers of over-taxing classes with data

collection: thirteen groups of students each targeting the same population and each hoping to maximise their sample size has a danger of wearing out the goodwill of their fellow students as well as of the professors who are regularly requested to provide access to their classes. This difficulty does not have an easy solution, and has, on occasion, required active intervention on behalf of the course teacher to manage frustrations.

5 CONCLUSION AND PERSPECTIVES

As an interdisciplinary space that addresses lifelong learning and the transfer of competences from classroom to professional practice, which develops research and data analysis skills, and which addresses questions of social context and ethical practice, the arguments for learning sciences being available to engineering and science students are evident. Beyond this, our learning science course has created a context in which the whole school has been reframed as a teaching and research and development lab on engineering and science education – a Smart Learning Space.

The development of the course has not been easy. Lack of resources, ensuring ethical practice, assessing interdisciplinary work and avoiding friction within the school are all ongoing challenges to be managed. At the same time, the evident learning of students and the obvious value of their research to other learners, to teachers and to the school as a whole is evident. Herbert Simon, both a renowned Computer Scientist and a Nobel Prize winner for Economics, once said that “Improvement in post-secondary education will require converting teaching from a solo sport to a community-based research activity” [13]. The study of learning sciences and learning research by students within our engineering school has provided an opportunity to build exactly this kind of community-based research on learning in our school.

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